

A stakeholder analysis based on project managers' perceptions: Unlocking transformative potential in Natura 2000 projects

Ruxandra Malina Petrescu-Mag^{a,b,c} , Kinga-Olga Reti^{a,1}, Tibor Hartel^a,
Alexandru Sabin Bădărău^a, Vlad Măciacășan^a, Dacina Crina Petrescu^{c,d,*}

^a Department of Environmental Science, Faculty of Environmental Science and Engineering, Babes-Bolyai University, 30 Fantanele Street, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

^b Doctoral School "International Relations and Security Studies", Babes-Bolyai University, 1 M. Kogalniceanu Street, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

^c Department of Economics and Rural Development, Gembloux Agro-Bio Tech, University of Liege, Gembloux, Belgium

^d Department of Hospitality Services, Faculty of Business, Babes-Bolyai University, 7 Horea Street, Cluj-Napoca 400174, Romania

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ABSTRACT

Divergent values and interests among stakeholders lead to conflicts during the implementation of biodiversity projects. The present study reveals the perception of project managers about stakeholders' needs, interests, positions, attitudes, and power that ultimately shape the relationships between these actors within Natura 2000 projects in Romania. Analyzing three selected projects, the research explores the existence of transformative change premises in terms of integrative, capability-responsiveness, and power equilibrium features. The thematic analysis of the interviews revealed a conflict network between stakeholders that poses a threat to the integrative attribute. "Academia" was found to be capable of fulfilling a mediator role, emphasizing the need for neutral entities in conflict resolution. Stakeholders segregate based on interests – those prioritizing economic functions show less concern for biodiversity. The need to use inclusive language in Natura 2000 projects was pointed out to prevent power imbalances and enhance overall inclusiveness. The study advocates for a project-specific approach to stakeholder analysis, thus avoiding the one-size-fits-all model.

1. Introduction

1.1. The research context

Conflicts over natural resources extend beyond a mere struggle between economic and conservation interests. They encompass a complex interplay of factors, from economic to environmental and social, such as abundance and scarcity of resources, climate variables, political crises, and social fragmentation generated, for example, by differences in interests, values, and knowledge (Vesco et al., 2020). Among them, the multi-actor nature of decisions characterized by poorly understood values, interrelations (Moallemi et al., 2023), and ambiguity in behavior and institutional structure (Reed et al., 2009) leads to diversity and uncertainty that generate conflicts. Therefore, these struggles cannot always be solved through economic measures since they are often a clash over differences in cultural practices and perceptions of the importance of natural resources (Scheidel et al., 2020).

Conflicts reflect differences in the values and interests of

stakeholders. To successfully implement biodiversity projects, a thorough comprehension of stakeholders' interests and perceptions is important (Berry et al., 2018). That is why stakeholder analysis (please see subsection 2.1 for the definition of "stakeholder analysis") facilitates the understanding of conflicting interests (Friedman and Miles, 2006), generating knowledge about their behaviors, norms, values, intentions, agendas, interests, and the influence or other resources they can use to shape decision-making processes (Brugha and Varvasovszky, 2000). Still, stakeholder analysis is not a platform for negotiation (Reed et al., 2009), but it can create the premises for a win-win negotiation and facilitate the adoption of future policy options.

Win-win negotiation can foster cooperation, trust, and social learning between stakeholders (Petrescu-Mag et al., 2017) and generate more sustainable, equitable, and acceptable outcomes for all parties involved. Such win-win negotiations can be valued as a step towards transformative change (please see subsection 2.1 for the definition of "transformative change"), enabling a shift from traditional conflictual models to more inclusive and innovative solutions. Similarly, achieving

* Corresponding author at: Department of Hospitality Services, Faculty of Business, Babes-Bolyai University, 7 Horea Street, Cluj-Napoca 400174, Romania.

E-mail address: crina.petrescu@ubbcluj.ro (D.C. Petrescu).

¹ This author contributed equally to this work, being considered first author.

sustainability of this transformation involves reconsidering and reshaping the dynamics of power relations (Temper et al., 2018). The capacity to go beyond zero-sum thinking, in which the success of one party is viewed as the loss of another [Chinoy et al. (2023) citing Foster (1965)], is, in our opinion, the essence of transformative power. Protected areas management decisions can catalyze sustainable transformations by embracing win-win discussions that balance community well-being, environmental concerns, and economic interests. Within this context, transformative change challenges the dominant forms of power that cause social and environmental injustice (Avelino, 2017) and promotes the empowerment of marginalized groups (Mertens, 2021; Petrescu-Mag et al., 2024a). The multi-actor nature of decisions is present within protected areas, like Natura 2000, the most extensive network of protected areas worldwide, encompassing approximately 27,000 terrestrial and marine sites, established to conserve Europe's most significant and endangered species and habitats (European Commission, 2022). Covering more than 18% of land areas within the European Union (EU) and about 9% of the surrounding seas, Natura 2000 is a significant initiative in conservation and environmental protection (European Commission, 2022). However, Natura 2000 does not impose strict limitations on all human activities but aims to achieve a balance between the conservation of biodiversity and other legitimate land uses (Hermoso et al., 2018). Land functions are essential within Natura 2000 protected areas due to their direct impact on the ecological integrity, biodiversity conservation, direct and indirect benefits for locals, and overall success of these designated zones (European Environment Agency, 2023). Hence, within the projects and policies on biodiversity conservation, frequently affected by conflicts (De Groot, 2006), a major challenge lies in articulating the socio-cultural and ecological significance of land functions. This is done by assigning monetary value to these functions, a complicated task since many of these benefits elude conventional market-driven economic assessments.

König et al. (2021) highlight that most human-nature conflicts are mainly present in agricultural settings, where alterations to natural landscapes are made to optimize the output of agricultural commodities or enhance ecosystem services to sustain human livelihoods. Land use-related disputes are a regular phenomenon worldwide, but with more severe circumstances in developing countries, where public power intervention is lacking and regulatory instruments are incomplete (Hilson, 2002; Kalabamu, 2019). The EU countries are not bypassed by land use conflicts related to, for example, land grab, land fragmentation, or the implementation of the Natura 2000 network (Bunkus and Theesfeld, 2018; Maczka et al., 2021; Manolache et al., 2018; Petrescu-Mag et al., 2017). The frequency of land use conflicts in Natura 2000 protected areas underscores the complex interaction between conservation objectives and various competing interests, including economic development, traditional practices, local livelihoods, and also the emotional and recreational values that people attach to these protected areas (Nita et al., 2024; Soliku and Schraml, 2018). Moreover, as per Mann and Jeanneaux (2009), land use conflicts have specific features that make their resolution more difficult. They involve complex natural systems and processes (e.g., trade-offs between crop production and ecosystem services, Kim and Arnhold, 2018), uncertainty (the lack of predictability in outcomes due to variables that are difficult to measure or foresee, Campbell et al., 2000), long-time scales (meaning that processes and outcomes unfold over extended periods, Campbell et al., 2000), and particular characteristics of social systems (e.g., indigenous land rights, ethnic fragmentation, de Jong et al., 2021). These characteristics must be understood and harmonized with nature protection projects' objectives to achieve the engagement of stakeholders (please see subsection 2.1 for the definition of "stakeholder"), which is crucial for sustainable land management (Ruiz et al., 2023). However, we should not ignore that conflict often catalyzes social transformation towards more sustainable approaches (Temper et al., 2018).

1.2. Study focus

While the majority of the stakeholder analysis in the scientific literature has focused on providing guidelines, frames, and instructions for stakeholder identification and classification (Andersen et al., 2009; Mitchell et al., 1997; Olander, 2007), less attention was paid to how project managers perceive and understand their stakeholder environment in practice (see, Di Maddaloni and Davis, 2018; Martens and Carvalho, 2017). The present study reveals project managers' perception of the stakeholders' needs, interests, positions, attitudes, and power dynamics that, ultimately, shape the relationship of these actors within Natura 2000 projects in Romania. Three projects for developing management plans for Natura 2000 sites (hereinafter called Natura 2000 projects) were selected to explore (using a stakeholder analysis) if the premises of transformative change are present in terms of capability-responsiveness, power equilibrium, and integrative attributes. By capitalizing on the knowledge and experience of project managers from these specific cases, the following exploratory questions (EQ) were addressed:

EQ1. Who are the stakeholders in each Natura 2000 selected project?

EQ2. What is the degree of stakeholders' power and their interest in influencing Natura 2000 projects in the project manager's perception?

EQ3. What is the level of capability-responsiveness of stakeholders in Natura 2000 projects in the project manager's perception?

EQ4. What are the relationships between stakeholders in Natura 2000 projects in the project manager's perception?

EQ5. How do stakeholders exercise power over each other in Natura 2000 projects in the project manager's perception?

EQ6. What is the level of stakeholders' sustainability mindset regarding land functions in Natura 2000 projects (economic, biodiversity, and cultural) in the project manager's perception?

EQ7. What solutions can facilitate and catalyze transformative change in Natura 2000 projects, considering factors such as stakeholder engagement, integration of diverse perspectives, and adaptive management practices?

The Romanian case of Natura 2000 projects highlights the importance of considering local contexts in achieving a balance between ecological integrity and human land use, offering valuable insights for other countries undertaking similar initiatives within the framework of international conservation goals. Romania's diverse regions, especially Transylvania, showcase rich biodiversity and a strong agricultural heritage, highlighting the need for integrated land management to harmonize conservation with sustainable land use. The coexistence of agriculture and conservation efforts exemplifies a global challenge and illustrates how addressing stakeholder dynamics and engaging diverse perspectives can drive transformative change, providing practical lessons for similar initiatives around the world.

2. The theoretical framework for the development of stakeholder analysis

The theoretical framework was developed to capture Natura 2000 project managers' perceptions of stakeholders' knowledge (on the project and other stakeholders), interaction, attitude, interests (in land functions and the project), position, and power in three Natura 2000 projects in Transylvania, Romania (please see subsection 2.1 for the definition of these concepts). We structured our analytical framework around four coordinates to understand the above and identify the best pathways toward transformative change: "I. Identify," "II. Prioritize," "III. Understand," and "IV. Reflect to transform" (see Fig. 1 and Table 1, first column).

Each coordinate is supported by a series of steps (eight in total, from

Fig. 1. The relationship of the four coordinates of the stakeholder analysis.

Table 1
Synthesis of the theoretical framework for stakeholder analysis.

Coordinates	Steps	Referenced literature
I. Identify	(1.1) Identify the key stakeholders relevant to Natura 2000 projects in Transylvania. (Question 1 of the interview script, Annex 1) (EQ1)	(Allan et al., 2022; Ariti et al., 2015; Caniato et al., 2014; Kariuki et al., 2021; Kerselaers et al., 2013; Namatama, 2020)
II. Prioritize	(2.1) Identify the typology of stakeholders according to their power and interest in the project objectives (Question 2 from the interview script, Annex 1) (EQ2) (2.2) Identify stakeholders' knowledge of others, interaction, attitude, knowledge about the project, interest in the project, and position = <i>capability-responsiveness character</i> (Question 3 of the interview script, Annex 1) (EQ3) (2.3) Identify the relationships between stakeholders = <i>integrative character</i> (Question 4 of the interview script, Annex 1) (EQ4) (2.4) Examine different levels of stakeholders' power about land use functions for each Natura 2000 project. = <i>power equilibrium</i> (Question 5 of the interview script, the column for "Power", Annex 1) (EQ5) (2.5) Identify the premises for stakeholders' sustainability mindset regarding land functions (economic, biodiversity, and cultural) according to the project manager's perceptions (Question 5 of the interview script, column for "Land function", Annex 1) (EQ6)	(Aaltonen, 2011; Al Mamun and Kim, 2020; Biggs and Matsuert, 1999, 1999; Caniato et al., 2014; Chevalier and Buckles, 2008; Daft and Weick, 1984; De Groot et al., 2002; Eden and Ackermann, 2013; Jepsen and Eskerod, 2009; Kismartini et al., 2023; Mitchell et al., 1997; Ramirez, 1999; Reed et al., 2009)
III. Understand	(3.1) Explore the beliefs of the project manager about the role of stakeholder analysis in their project. (Question 6 from the interview script, Annex 1) (EQ3-EQ6)	(Aaltonen, 2011; Reed et al., 2009)
IV. Reflect to transform	(4.1) Identify solutions for transformative change based on cross-project analysis (EQ7)	(van Bruggen et al., 2019)

1.1 to 4.1) designed to comprehensively analyze the dynamics of stakeholders and the potential for transformative change. These steps, detailed in the second column of Table 1 and relying on project managers' perception, include: (1.1) identifying key stakeholders; (2.1) classifying them by power and interest; (2.2) assessing their knowledge and interactions; (2.3) understanding their relationships; (2.4)

examining power levels concerning land use; (2.5) evaluating sustainability mindsets; (3.1) exploring project managers' beliefs about stakeholder analysis; and (4.1) identifying solutions for transformative change through cross-project analysis.

This structured approach allows us to systematically explore and understand the complexities of stakeholder engagement and its implications for transformative initiatives within environmental projects like Natura 2000. Considering the four coordinates, the first coordinate ("Identify") aimed to uncover key stakeholders affected by the Natura 2000 project, as they can significantly impact the environment, economy, and social well-being of the region. The objective of the "Prioritize" coordinate was to obtain information from project managers to reveal the needs and expectations of different stakeholder groups, identify participation gaps, develop strategies to increase stakeholder involvement, and recognize potential conflicts or opportunities for collaboration and support. The "Understand" coordinate involved exploring project managers' perspectives on stakeholder dynamics and the significance of stakeholder analysis. Ultimately, "Reflect to transform" coordinate aimed to propose actionable recommendations to foster collaborative decision-making and drive positive changes in Natura 2000 projects. The operationalization of these coordinates into interviews is further detailed in subsection "3.2 Interview implementation and the operationalization of the theoretical framework in the interviews".

To uncover foundational elements that can catalyze sustainable and inclusive transformations in environmental management practices, we focused on the integrative, capability-responsiveness, and power equilibrium features of Natura 2000 projects. In doing so, we followed Pascual et al. (2022), who emphasized that, in the context of transformative change within the Biodiversity, Climate, and Society (BCS) nexus, three key attributes – integrative, equitable, and adaptive – can influence this process. These three attributes were adapted to the context of the present study as follows. We examined the *integrative* nature of the analyzed projects, assessing their level of multistakeholder collaboration (involving governmental agencies, NGOs, local communities, etc., to achieve the goals of Natura 2000 projects). The second attribute was *power equilibrium*, which was considered to amplify the voices of those marginalized and offer an inclusive environment. The third attribute referred to the *capability-responsiveness character*. This attribute ensures stakeholders are well-informed and responsive to the evolving circumstances within Natura 2000 projects, facilitating proactive adaptation and collaborative engagement critical for transformative change.

2.1. Central concepts used in the study

This subsection offers explanations that clarify the meaning of key terms used in the present analysis. Because some concepts (e.g., attitude and power) can have different meanings according to the field in which they are used, the objectives of the research, or the researchers' perspective, Table 2 intends to indicate the meaning adopted in the present study.

3. Methodology

3.1. Study country context

Romania has more than 600 Natura 2000 protected areas, including Romanian Sites of Community Importance (ROSCI – 435) and Romanian Special Protected Areas for Birds (ROSPA – 171) (Ursu et al., 2020). They are strategically distributed across all biogeographical regions within the country, collectively constituting 26.04 % of the total surface area of Romania (ROSPA – 3875,298 ha, ROSCI – 4650,819 ha). Additionally, Romanian Sites of Community Importance account for 4.69 % of the European Sites of Community Importance, while Romanian Special Protected Areas make up 5.1 % of the total European Special

Table 2
Central concepts defined.

Concept	Meaning adopted in this study
Attitude	It refers to the stakeholder’s evaluation of the project, which can be positive or negative (Manfredo and Dayer, 2004). We opted to use the word “attitude” (and not “opinion”) because the stakeholder capabilities-responsiveness included Knowledge of others, Interaction, Attitude, Knowledge regarding the project, Interest, and Position, based on Caniato et al., (2014) paper, who used the word “attitude”. Similarly to Freeze Kulkarni (2007), we adopted a knowledge capability perspective that aligns with the capability framework outlined by Alavi and Leidner (2001), including knowledge of others and knowledge regarding the project. The framework encompasses the ability to effectively use information and the potential to impact future actions (in our case, together with interaction, attitude, interest, and position, which we call “responsiveness”).
Capability-responsiveness	Similarly to Freeze Kulkarni (2007), we adopted a knowledge capability perspective that aligns with the capability framework outlined by Alavi and Leidner (2001), including knowledge of others and knowledge regarding the project. The framework encompasses the ability to effectively use information and the potential to impact future actions (in our case, together with interaction, attitude, interest, and position, which we call “responsiveness”).
Carrier function of land	The term “carrier” in the context of land functions refers to the role of land in supporting activities such as transport, industrial sites, and settlements (De Groot, 2006; Reed et al., 2009).
Charisma	Charisma is an innate quality rooted in human cultural transmission mechanisms that allows individuals to captivate and influence others naturally (Castelnuovo et al., 2017). It is a compelling charm that inspires devotion and enthusiasm in others. Charisma results from emotional interactions between leaders and followers, fostering legitimacy and promoting social changes (Wasielewski, 1985).
Coercive power	It uses emotional, financial, and physical threats and punishments (Galbraith, 1983; Reed et al., 2009). It is also named “condign power”.
Compensatory/ Reward power	It means “buying submission” (Galbraith, 1983) by granting a reward or payment.
Complementarity	Complementarity refers to a relationship where stakeholders work independently towards their objectives, which align with and support the overall goals of the project (Reed et al., 2009). The actions of each stakeholder, while autonomous, contribute to the project’s success through mutually reinforcing outcomes and mutual provision of resources to meet the project objectives (Bundy et al., 2018).
Conditioning power	It operates by manipulating beliefs and perceptions (Reed et al., 2009).
Conflict	The main type of conflict we refer to can be linked to Restricted Access Conflicts (RAC) (Soliku and Schraml, 2018) that arise from conservation initiatives that prohibit or limit the access and utilization of resources (e.g., land, water, forests) in protected areas for local communities.
Cooperation	Cooperation refers to interdependent actions that benefit all stakeholders, where stakeholders actively work together to achieve the objectives of the project (Bosse and Coughlan, 2016).
Influence	This is a stakeholder’s ability to affect or shape decisions, outcomes, or actions within a given context. According to Nelson and Quick (1995), cited by Reed et al. (2009), “the capacity for influence is dependent on power.”
Interaction	It refers to dynamic and reciprocal engagement, communication, and stakeholder collaboration (Caniato et al., 2014; Garcés-Ayerbe et al., 2019).
Interest	The term refers to what constitutes a real “stake” in the activities of other persons or groups (Caniato et al., 2014).
Integrative approach	It encourages collaboration and cooperation among different stakeholders (Emerson et al., 2012).
Knowledge on others	It refers to project managers’ perception of how stakeholders understand the responsibilities, functions, and duties of other stakeholders involved in the project (Caniato et al., 2014).
Knowledge regarding the project	It refers to the information and understanding of stakeholders about the project (e.g., objectives,

Table 2 (continued)

Concept	Meaning adopted in this study
	activities, and outcomes) (Martinsuo and Kantolahti, 2009; Reed et al., 2009).
Position	It refers to the stakeholder as a supporter or adversary of the project (Schmeer, 1999).
Power	It refers to the degree and way that stakeholders can influence a project during conflicts and explore the potential to enhance their influence by collaborating with others (Andersen et al., 2009). Power is seen as a structural capability, distinct from its behavioral use and its impact on the distribution of payoffs (Lawler and Yoon, 1996).
Power equilibrium	Power equilibrium is the situation in which parties have similar degrees of power. The opposing situation is a power imbalance, defined as the difference in the power of each actor over the other (Casciaro and Piskorski, 2005).
Power-interest matrix	The power-interest matrix is a strategic tool used in stakeholder analysis to map stakeholders based on their level of power and their level of interest (from low to high) (Ackermann and Eden, 2011; Bryson et al., 2002; Mendelow, 1981; Srich et al., 2024). Stakeholders are typically categorized into four quadrants: Context settlers: Stakeholders with low interest but high power; Key players: Stakeholders with high power and high interest; Crowd: Stakeholders with low power and low interest; Subjects: Stakeholders with high interest and low power (Caniato et al., 2014; Chevalier and Buckles, 2008; Eden and Ackermann, 2013; Kismartini et al., 2023).
Stakeholder	Mainardes et al. (2011) observed 66 concepts associated with the term “stakeholder” in various references. Freeman (2010) offers one of the most cited definitions of the stakeholder as “any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organization’s objectives.” For environmental projects, Röling and Wagemakers (1998), cited by Ramirez (1999), considered that “Stakeholders are (...) natural resource users and managers.”
Stakeholder analysis	Although defining stakeholder analysis (SA) remains challenging, as noted by Reed (2009), there appears to be a consensus that SA serves as a decision-support tool whose primary objective is to improve the understanding of the examined system by identifying key stakeholders and understanding their perspectives (Bendtsen et al., 2021).
Transformative change	It refers to fundamental changes in societal, political, and economic systems, along with shifts in paradigms and values that are essential to address the global socio-ecological crisis [(Watson et al., 2019) cited by (Arias-Arévalo et al., 2023)].

Protected Areas.

Transylvania, a region in central Romania, is known for its rich biodiversity and cultural heritage (Hartel et al., 2020). Within Transylvania, numerous Natura 2000 protected areas have been established to safeguard and preserve the unique ecosystems present in this landscape. Transylvania has a strong agricultural tradition, and the coexistence of Natura 2000 areas and agricultural activities is a crucial aspect of sustainable land management (Loos et al., 2021; Toth et al., 2020). Urbanization, rural exodus, tourism attractiveness, the EU conservation regulations of the ecosystems with high natural value, or the “production for profit” attitude (Milcu et al., 2014) ask for a careful understanding of Natura 2000 projects in Romania from design to follow-up.

3.2. Interview implementation and the operationalization of the theoretical framework in the interviews

The current study followed the guidelines outlined in COREQ (Consolidated Criteria for Reporting Qualitative Research), which provides a checklist of essential items for reporting qualitative research

comprehensively (Tong et al., 2007). Interviewing project managers proved challenging due to their inherent busyness and reluctance. This constraint and the fact that the study area was Transylvania, not the entire country, influenced the number of interviews. We used multiple channels to establish connections with project managers, primarily leveraging university networks and personal connections. Although the number of interviews was limited, they were in-depth and multifaceted, with interviewees bringing diverse and extensive expertise in project management. Their experience spanned a variety of natural and socio-cultural contexts. The richness of the data gathered from these experts enabled us to effectively address the research questions.

To ensure confidentiality and protect the privacy of project managers, we opted to use acronyms as substitutes for the real names of the projects (APU, BITransylv, ApeBi). Furthermore, project managers' identities were anonymized using the project acronym and the abbreviation "PM" (e.g., APU_PM, the project manager code used in the text). Our commitment to maintaining anonymity and securing sensitive information motivated this deliberate approach. Throughout our investigation, we encountered instances where respondents shared delicate details about other individuals involved in the projects. Considering this, we took meticulous steps to eliminate elements that could link a respondent to a specific project. By implementing these measures, we aimed to provide a secure space for respondents to share information without fear of compromising their anonymity or the confidentiality of information about the projects in which they participated. Two researchers conducted individual interviews online. The interviews lasted between 70 and 100 minutes. Details on the main aspects of the three projects and their project managers are presented in Table 3.

The theoretical framework used to develop the interview script and the script were presented in Subsection 2, Table 1, and Annex 1, respectively. For the "Identify" coordinate, we performed a literature review to identify stakeholders, we presented the list to the project

managers and we asked them to adjust the list (remove and add stakeholders) to reflect the situation in their project.

We performed a thematic analysis of the project managers' responses from the second coordinate ("Prioritize") and analyzed data collected from the first three coordinates ("Identify", "Prioritize", and "Understand") by comparing them (refer to Table 1). Several instruments were used to perform steps (2.1) – (2.5). For "(2.1) Identify the typology of stakeholders", we used the "power-interest" matrix that depicts the interconnections between stakeholders (Reed et al., 2009). This matrix offers a visual representation of stakeholders based on their power level to influence the project and their interest in it (as project managers perceived them), helping to identify key stakeholders who can substantially influence decisions and outcomes. A standard method used in the "power-interest" matrix is to classify stakeholders into "Key players", "Context setters", "Subjects" and "Crowd" (Caniato et al., 2014; Chevalier and Buckles, 2008; Eden and Ackermann, 2013; Kismartini et al., 2023) (please refer to Table 1 for the meaning of these concepts).

For "(2.2) Identify the knowledge, interaction, attitude, interest, and position of stakeholders", the interview questions explored project managers' perceptions of the knowledge, interaction, attitude, interest, and position of stakeholders. Schmeer (1999) believes that knowing the stakeholders' knowledge, interests, and position empowers policy-makers and managers to engage more efficiently with stakeholders and improves the likelihood of support for the specified policy, program, or project. "Knowledge of others" helps to assess the level of comprehension and awareness among stakeholders about the roles and responsibilities of others involved in the project. The "interaction" is crucial to successful project implementation and stakeholder cooperation. Examining the level of interaction between stakeholders contributes to evaluating the social dynamics of the project. The "attitudes" about the project help us to understand the overall sentiment about the project. Positive attitudes can foster collaboration and support, while negative attitudes can lead to resistance. Al Mamun and Kim (2020) concluded that most conflicts are due to a lack of interest and knowledge gaps. Therefore, both knowledge and interest were included in the interview script. "Knowledge regarding the project" provides insights into whether stakeholders understand the project's objectives and potential impacts. Then, the "interest" stakeholders have in the project can predict their commitment, where high interest generally correlates with increased participation and the project's success.

Similarly, Caniato et al. (2014) investigated "knowledge of others", "interest", "attitude", and "interaction" to understand the responsibilities and behaviors of stakeholders in the infectious waste management sector in Bangkok. The "position" is a variable that can contribute to identifying supporters or opponents of the project. The investigation of these six variables can provide a comprehensive understanding of the social landscape, potential challenges, and opportunities to foster positive change within Natura 2000 projects.

For "(2.3) Identify the relationships between stakeholders", we used an actor linkage matrix. According to Reed et al. (2009), there are several methods to investigate stakeholder relationships, among which the most used ones are actor-linkage matrices (ALM) (Biggs and Matzaert, 1999), social network analysis, and knowledge mapping. In the ALM, used in this study, the relationship between stakeholders is expressed using specific keywords like "conflict", "complementarity", or "cooperation" (Reed et al., 2009). The difference between "complementarity" and "cooperation" is that in the former case, stakeholders work independently to achieve complementary objectives of the project. In contrast, in the latter, they work together to accomplish the project's objectives. Considering the advantages and disadvantages of various stakeholder analysis methods, as thoroughly presented by Reed et al. (2009), the following explanations support the selection of ALM. We used ALM because this is ALM particularly effective for examining the relationships and interactions between different stakeholders. It allows us to see how stakeholders are connected and the nature of their interactions, which is important for understanding the conflict network

Table 3
Critical elements of the Natura 2000 projects.

Project title	Critical elements of the project	Information about the interviewed project manager	
		Experience in Natura 2000 projects	Level of education
APU	- Project status: Completed. -The objectives were primarily to inventory, map, and assess the conservation status of habitats and species in the targeted area. Subsequently, they developed conservation measures aimed at maintaining or improving the condition of these habitats and species, with a focus on incorporating sustainable land use practices (e.g., integration of sustainable wood harvesting as a key element of its land use strategy, aligning long-term health and land productivity).	14 years	Bachelor degree in Biology
BITransylv	- Project status: Completed. The main objectives were to inventory and map habitats and species of conservation interest, describe abiotic factors and conduct a study among the local community to determine their perception of protected areas.	17 years	Ph.D. in Geology
ApeBi	- Project status: Completed. - The main objective was to develop management plans for protected areas.	13 years	Ph.D. in Physical Geography

and the power dynamics at play. While knowledge mapping is useful for visualizing the distribution and flow of knowledge (Samuel Driessen et al., 2007), it does not inherently focus on the relationships between stakeholders or the nature of their interactions (Pino et al., 2014). Moreover, by identifying and analyzing the linkages between actors, the ALM helps reveal the power dynamics and influence patterns among stakeholders. This is essential for exploring power equilibrium features and understanding how different stakeholders can affect transformative change. Knowledge mapping tends to focus more on identifying what knowledge is held and shared rather than on who holds the power or how influence is exerted within the network. So, ALM and knowledge mapping have their respective strengths, but the ALM is more suited to the specific needs of this research.

For step “(2.4) Examine different levels of power of stakeholders in relation to land use functions for each project”, we used Reed et al. (2009) analysis framework, which was developed to evaluate the different dimensions of stakeholders’ “power”. We added two other sources of power: “expertise” and “family, peers”. Experts can influence decisions and behaviors through credibility, trustworthiness, and persuasive communication, while family and peers provide social capital and shape individual norms, values, and engagement (Adler and Adler, 1998; Lachmi et al., 2024). Experts are viewed as credible and influential, with their opinions shaping perceptions and actions (McGinnies and Ward, 1980). They communicate knowledge, convincing stakeholders of their ideas’ validity (Bammer, 2013). Experts offer authoritative conflict solutions, mediating disputes with fact-based reasoning (Prince, 2010). Family and peers shape norms, values, and behaviors (McDonald, 1980), influencing engagement with nature’s protection (Pretty, 2003). These relationships build social capital, providing access to opportunities, resources, and networks (Coleman, 1988).

For “(2.5) Identify the premises for stakeholders’ sustainability mindset, according to project manager perceptions”, we referred to the land functions. To the original framework analysis (Reed et al., 2009), we added “biodiversity conservation function” and “cultural function” [as per (Mann and Jeanneaux, 2009)]. To investigate the premises for stakeholders’ sustainability mindset, we grouped all land functions (production, dwelling, carrier, biodiversity conservation, and cultural) into economic, biodiversity, and cultural categories.

Six questions (questions 6.1–6.6 from the interview script, Annex 1) were dedicated to the third coordinate (“Understand”), more specifically to “(3.1) Explore the beliefs of the project manager about the role of stakeholder analysis in their project.” These six questions were designed to reveal the project manager’s beliefs about stakeholder analysis role in their project and what aspects of stakeholder analysis could be improved in the future (considering the project manager’s experience in the project). For example, suppose a project manager believes that stakeholder analysis is unimportant. In that case, they may not allocate adequate resources to engage stakeholders in project dynamics, leading to stakeholder dissatisfaction and demotivation that jeopardize the project. The project manager’s perspective on the project can then reveal critical information about the project’s objectives, timelines, constraints, and risks. It can also provide insight into the project’s stakeholder dynamics, resource allocation, and communication strategies. Therefore, understanding the perspective of the project manager on the main characteristics of Natura 2000 projects helps identify potential risks and challenges early, allowing stakeholders to take corrective action before it is too late. Ultimately, understanding the beliefs of a project manager about stakeholder analysis and their perspective on the project can improve project outcomes and stakeholder satisfaction, with a positive impact during and after implementation.

For the fourth coordinate (“Reflect to transform”), we analyzed the results from the three projects to recommend directions toward positive transformative changes in Natura 2000 projects in Transylvania. Such recommendations can foster a collaborative environment for effective decision-making.

3.3. Steps of the thematic analysis

In the initial phase, the interviews were transcribed verbatim, which means that every word, pause, stutter, and filler words were transcribed. Vatis Tech, an online platform, was used for verbatim transcription, allowing speech-to-text conversion of Romanian audio files. Subsequently, an intelligent transcription was performed in the second step. This transcription captures every word but involves interpretation to omit pauses, hesitations, and filler words, and it also improves grammar. The Romanian text resulting from intelligent transcription was used for analysis. Quotes from project manager responses included in this study represent the English translation of the intelligent transcription of the Romanian text.

We used a hybrid approach, combining elements of deductive reasoning (for questions 2–5, The pre-established codes were “cooperation”, “collaboration”, “conflict”, which served for the thematic analysis of the “integrative approach”, for example) and, deductive and inductive reasoning to analyze the answers from the question 6.1–6.6 from the script (Annex 1). For this part, the main codes (pre-established codes) identified through deductive coding included: Atmosphere characterization (question 6.1); Stakeholder analysis performed (question 6.2); Challenges in stakeholder analysis (question 6.3); Retrospective assessment (question 6.4); Priority issues (question 6.5); and Goldfish scenario (question 6.6). The goldfish scenario originates in Alexander Pushkin’s “The Fisherman and the Goldfish”, probably inspired by “The Fisherman and His Wife”, a German fairy tale collected by the Brothers Grimm in 1812 (where a poor fisherman catches a magical talking fish that grants wishes in exchange for its freedom). The “goldfish scenario” represents the hypothetical capacity to remove obstacles that hinder the Natura 2000 project’s success. This scenario envisions an ideal situation where challenges such as regulatory hurdles, stakeholder conflicts, resource limitations, or biodiversity threats can be swiftly addressed or mitigated. Project managers were invited to imagine they could ask a magical goldfish to grant them wishes. This engaging exercise promotes reflection on priorities, desires, and goals, serving as an effective tool for creative thinking and goal-setting in workshops and discussions. Inductive coding was used to identify subcodes that illustrated new themes or nuances within the data that were not anticipated by the initial set of pre-established codes. The main codes and subcodes helped to conduct the thematic analysis of project managers’ perceptions of the role of stakeholder analysis in each Natura 2000 project.

4. Results

4.1. Stakeholders’ power, interests, capability-responsiveness, the integrative character, and power equilibrium of Natura 2000 projects

The results of the stakeholder analysis for the three selected Natura 2000 projects, namely BITransylv, ApeBi, and APU, were mapped using the power-interest matrix to categorize stakeholders according to their level of power and interest in influencing the projects. By placing the stakeholders in a specific matrix region, project managers classified the stakeholders into four quadrants: Key Players, Context Settlers, Subjects, and Crowd. The typology of stakeholders considering their power to influence the project and their interest in the project was illustrated within the power-interest matrix (Fig. 2). The matrix shows the stakeholders’ roles according to the project managers’ perceptions.

The power-interest matrix revealed intriguing insights since, depending on each Natura 2000 project, there were situations when the same stakeholder category was placed on a different axis region. The matrix showed that different stakeholders had varying degrees of power and interest in all projects. Key players, such as the Local Public Administration, Academia, CPA_Enviro, and Forest Directorate, consistently exhibited high power and high interest, indicating their critical role in the successful implementation of Natura 2000 projects. Context

Fig. 2. The power-interest matrix. Identified stakeholders in the **APU project**: Local public administration, Members of the scientific community (abbreviated as Academia), Central public administration, Ministry of the Environment (abbreviated in the text as CPA_Enviro), Farmers, NGO, The local business people, Land investors, National Administration of Romanian Waters (NARW). Identified stakeholders in the **BITransylv project**: Farmers, NGOs, Local business people, Local Public Administration, Members of the scientific community (Academy), Central public administration, Ministry of Agriculture (abbreviated as CPA_Agri), Central public administration, Ministry of the Environment, National Agency for Environmental Protection, The National Agency for Protected Natural Areas (abbreviated in the text as CPA_Enviro), Forest Directorate, National Road Infrastructure Administration Company (NRIAC), Pre-university educational institutions, The local community. Identified stakeholders in the **ApeBi project**: Local public administration, Members of the scientific community (Academia), Central public administration, Ministry of the Environment (abbreviated in the text as CPA_Enviro), Farmers, NGO, The local business people, Land investors, Forest Directorate, National Administration of Romanian Waters (NARW).

settlers, like CPA_Agri in BITransylv and NARW in APU, possessed high power but lower interest. Subjects, such as farmers and local business people, had a high interest but low power. APU_PM explained the high interest of farmers: “(...) the farmers’ interest is high because, in the area, many individuals own various types of private land, including forests, pastures, and even a small amount of arable land.” The crowd, consisting of stakeholders with low power and low interest, such as pre-university educational institutions in BITransylv, was peripheral to the immediate project activities but could become more significant with increased engagement and awareness.

These differences underscore the need for an adaptive and personalized approach for each case, emphasizing the importance of flexibility in project management. Regarding the characterization of stakeholders, in two of the examined projects, farmers were placed along the high-interest-low-power axis, underscoring their substantial interest in the outcomes but limited influence over the decision-making processes.

The multifaceted nature of stakeholder capability-responsiveness in the three Natura 2000 projects can be unpacked by examining how various dimensions — Knowledge of others, Interaction, Attitude, Knowledge regarding the project, Interest, and Position — contribute to the overall responsiveness scores (Table 4). The capability-responsiveness scores among various stakeholder groups revealed notable variations within Natura 2000 projects. The results indicated that the NGOs exhibited the highest capability-responsiveness score at 16. BITransylv_PM emphasized the importance of NGOs’ role in their project, saying, “Even if NGOs don’t have legislative power, they can engage in strong lobbying efforts, which is very important.” Translating this score into words, we can say that NGOs were generally well-informed about other stakeholders’ roles and perspectives (Knowledge of others). NGOs often actively engaged with various stakeholders, fostering collaboration and communication (Interaction). NGOs appeared to generally adopt a proactive approach to environmental issues and project engagement (Attitude). NGOs were likely to have in-

depth knowledge about Natura 2000 projects and their objectives (Knowledge regarding the project). Their core mission often aligned closely with the goals of Natura 2000 projects (Interest). NGOs appeared to be influential in advocating and shaping project outcomes (Position). NGOs were closely followed by CPA_Enviro at 15.66 and Academia at 14.33. These stakeholders had a substantial level of capability-responsiveness regarding Natura 2000 projects, demonstrating strong understanding and proactive engagement. Conversely, farmers and land investors had the lowest scores of 8.66 and 9, respectively, indicating limited capability-responsiveness in project-related activities. The local public administration and pre-university educational institutions also exhibited moderate scores, suggesting a balanced but not leading role in the project’s dynamics. They occupied a middle ground, contributing to projects in more balanced but less influential ways.

We developed an ALM for each project (see Annex 2, Table 1A-3A). Table 5 illustrates only the conflict relationships in the three case studies.

Based on the actor-linkage matrix in Table 5, the ApeBi project had the most conflicting positions, particularly involving NGOs. Specifically, NGOs in the ApeBi project conflicted with Academia, the Forest Directorate, Local public administration, and NARW. ApeBi_PM said: “Farmers, investors, and local administration consider the protected status to be a barrier that hinders them from exploiting the resources as they would like (...) They see protected areas only as obstacles. NGOs, in turn, did not agree with either the actions of local administrations or the NRAW, as the NRAW regulated water use without considering ecological necessities and without collaboration with the CPA_Enviro. NGOs also had their concerns that environmental approvals were granted too easily.” In ApeBi, the project manager describes the conflictual relationship between the mayor and CPA_Enviro: “Municipalities are not in agreement with establishing protected areas within their territories. When the CPA_Enviro designated them, the mayors were not consulted. Mayors perceive protected areas as obstacles to development, arguing

Table 4
Natura 2000 project managers' perception of stakeholders' capability-responsiveness.

Project and stakeholder category**	Stakeholder capability-responsiveness (scores*)							Average total score of stakeholder category****
	Knowledge on others	Interaction	Attitude	Knowledge regarding the project	Interest	Position	Total score***	
APU: Farmers	1	2	1	1	2	1	8	8.66*
BITransylv: Farmers	2	2	1	2	3	1	11	
ApeBi: Farmers	1	1	1	1	2	1	7	
APU: The local business people.	2	2	2	2	2	3	13	10
BITransylv: The local community of business people	1	2	2	1	2	2	10	
ApeBi: The local business people.	1	1	1	1	2	1	7	
APU: NGOs	2	3	3	3	3	3	17	16.33
BITransylv: NGOs	3	3	3	3	3	3	18	
ApeBi: NGOs	2	3	3	2	2	2	14	
APU: Local public administration	1	2	2	2	3	2	12	13.33
BITransylv: Local public administration	3	3	3	3	3	3	18	
ApeBi: Local public administration	1	1	2	2	2	2	10	
APU: Academia	3	3	3	3	3	2	17	14.33
BITransylv: Academia	3	2	3	2	3	2	15	
ApeBi: Academia	2	2	2	2	1	2	11	
APU: CPA_Enviro	3	3	2	3	3	3	17	15.66
BITransylv: CPA_Enviro	2	3	2	2	2	3	14	
ApeBi: CPA_Enviro	2	2	3	3	3	3	16	
BITransylv: CPA_Agri	2	2	1	1	1	2	9	9
BITransylv: Forest Directorate	3	3	1	3	3	1	14	12.5
ApeBi: Forest Directorate	2	2	1	2	2	2	11	
BITransylv: NRIAC	2	2	1	1	3	1	10	10
BITransylv: Pre-university educational institutions	2	2	3	2	2	3	14	14
BITransylv: The local community	1	2	2	1	2	2	10	10
APU: Land investors	2	2	2	2	2	2	12	9
ApeBi: Land investors	1	1	1	1	1	1	6	
APU: NARW	2	2	2	2	1	2	11	12.5
ApeBi: NARW	1	2	3	2	3	3	14	

* Scores are measured on a scale of 1–3 (1 = Low/insignificant, 2 = Moderate, 3 = High).

** Please refer to the legend of Fig. 2 for the abbreviations of stakeholders' categories

*** The total score was calculated by summing the points received for each dimension of the stakeholder capability-responsiveness for each stakeholder category in each project. The total scores can range from 6 to 18 (e.g., for APU: Farmers, the score is 1 + 2 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 1 = 8).

**** We calculated the average total score for each stakeholder category considering all projects. We did this by summing the scores obtained in each project for a specific stakeholder category and then dividing this sum by the number of occurrences of that stakeholder category (e.g., for farmers, the score is (8 + 11 + 7) / 3 = 8.66). The average total scores can range from 6 to 18.

Table 5
Conflict relations between stakeholders in APU, BITransylv, and ApeBi projects according to the actor-linkage matrix.

Project and stakeholder category*	Academia	NGOs	CPA_Enviro	Forest Directorate	The local community	Local public administration	NARW
APU: Local public administration	●		●				
BITransylv: Farmers		●	●				
BITransylv: NGOs				●			
BITransylv: CPA_Enviro					●		
ApeBi: Farmers			●				
ApeBi: NGOs			●	●			
ApeBi: Local business people			●			●	●
ApeBi: Local public administration			●				
ApeBi: Academia				●			●
ApeBi: Land investors			●				

* Please refer to the legend of Fig. 2 for the abbreviations of stakeholders' categories.

that they must spend more money on environmental studies.” Practically, the ApeBi project displayed significant disagreements with various stakeholders.

In contrast, in the APU project, the only conflictual relationship signaled by the project manager was between Local public administration, and Academia and CPA_Enviro, which showed a lower degree of contention compared to the ApeBi project. This indicates that the nature of stakeholder interactions in the APU project is relatively more harmonious. Within BITRansylv, the project manager’s responses highlighted that NGOs and CPA_Enviro were the primary stakeholders in the conflict.

By comparing these projects, CPA_Enviro was perceived by project managers as having one of the most conflictual positions, which implied a recurring pattern of conflict or disagreement associated with the role of this public authority. The conflict relations in the actor-linkage matrix highlighted in Table 5 revealed that ApeBi had the highest level of contention and involved multiple stakeholders. BITRansylv sat in the middle with moderate conflicts, and APU had the least conflicts, suggesting a more stable and cooperative environment among its stakeholders.

Table 5 primarily highlights the conflictual relationships between stakeholders due to the role that conflicts play in hindering the progress and success of Natura 2000 projects. Conflicts can significantly impact the decision-making processes, implementation efficiency, and overall project outcomes, making it imperative to understand and address these issues. Although complementarity and cooperation are important and beneficial aspects of stakeholder relationships, conflicts present immediate challenges that can jeopardize project efforts if not managed effectively. However, subsection “4.3 Cross-projects results” highlights the main cooperation and complementarity relations between stakeholders.

Tables 6 to 8 present the stakeholders’ levels of interest and power in the land use functions for each case study. In the APU project (Table 6), according to the project manager’s perception, farmers showed high interest in production and dwelling, highlighting their dependence on land. They possessed moderate coercive and compensatory power. Conversely, NGOs were highly interested in biodiversity conservation and significant compensatory and conditioning power. Local business people showed a high interest in dwelling and carrier functions, with substantial influence through property ownership and expertise. Local public administration showed high interest and power in cultural and carrier functions, leveraging their management positions and property ownership, which was further emphasized by the conclusion of the project manager: “Local authorities in rural areas prefer to view the business environment and economic interests as a lifesaver for the community, rarely showing interest in the natural values of the areas.” Academia focused on biodiversity conservation and cultural functions, using their expertise and charisma to influence policy.

The BITRansylv project (see Table 7) revealed diverse interests and power dynamics. According to the project manager, farmers prioritized production and dwelling, holding moderate coercive power and property ownership. Regarding land investors, the project manager considered that “Land investors perceived the protected area as an obstacle because it restricted their acquisition and use of the land.” NGOs focused on the conservation of biodiversity, with a high compensatory power. Local business people were interested in the production, dwelling, and carrier functions, leveraging property and expertise. Local public administration showed high interest in all functions, particularly cultural and carrier, supported by management positions and property ownership. BITransylv_PM clearly expressed this reality, saying: “The mayor had a persuasive power and a very high interest in the development of the community, both culturally, in terms of land production, and biodiversity preservation ... He saw this protected area somehow as a potential hotspot for ecotourism development ... Additionally, I was impressed by the school directors and teachers at the pre-university who also had knowledge related to biodiversity and cultural values in the

Table 6
Levels of interest and power of the stakeholders in relation to land use functions in the APU project (scores^{*}).

Stakeholder category [*]	Interest				Power				Family/Peers				
	Land function				Sources of power								
	Production	Dwelling	Conservation of biodiversity	Cultural	Carrier ^{**} (transportation, industrial sites, HORECA)	Coercive power ^{**}	Compensatory power ^{**}	Conditioning power ^{**}		Charisma ^{**}	Property (goods)	Expertise	Management position in a company/institution
Farmers	3	3	1	3	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	1
NGOs	1	1	3	3	1	1	1	3	2	1	3	1	1
Local business people	2	3	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	1
Local public administration	3	3	1	3	3	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2
Academia	1	1	3	3	1	1	1	3	3	1	3	2	1
Land investors	3	3	1	2	2	1	3	1	2	2	2	2	1
Central public administration (Ministry of the Environment)	1	1	3	2	3	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	1
NARW	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	1

*** The definition of these terms is included in Table 2.
^{*} Scores are measured on a scale of 1–3 (1 = Low/insignificant, 2 = Moderate, 3 = High).
^{**} Please refer to the legend of Fig. 2 for the abbreviations of stakeholders’ categories.

Table 7
Levels of interest and power of the stakeholders in relation to land use functions in the BITransylv project (scores^{*}).

Stakeholder category ^{**}	Interest				Power								
	Land function				Sources of power								
	Production	Dwelling	Conservation of biodiversity	Cultural	Carrier ^{***} (transportation, industrial sites)	Coercive power ^{***}	Compensatory power ^{***}	Conditioning power ^{***}	Charisma ^{***}	Property (goods)	Expertise	Management position in a company/institution membership in an NGO, church, association)	Family/Peers
Farmers	3	3	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	1
NGOs	1	1	3	3	1	1	2	3	3	1	3	3	2
Local business people	3	3	1	2	3	1	2	1	2	3	2	3	2
Local public administration	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	2
Academia	1	1	3	2	1	1	1	2	3	1	3	1	1
CPA_Agri	3	2	1	1	2	2	3	1	1	1	3	3	1
CPA_Enviro	2	2	3	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	1
Forest Directorate	3	1	2	1	3	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	1
NRIAC	1	2	1	1	3	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	1
Pre-university educational institutions	2	3	2	3	2	1	1	3	2	1	2	2	3
Local community	3	3	1	2	3	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	3

* Scores are measured on a scale of 1–3 (1 = Low/insignificant, 2 = Moderate, 3 = High).

** Please refer to the legend of Fig. 2 for the abbreviations of stakeholders' categories.

*** The definition of these terms is included in Table 2.

area". CPA_Enviro focused on the conservation of biodiversity with significant compensatory power. The local community had a high interest in production and dwelling, with moderate influence through expertise and family/peers.

In the ApeBi project (Table 8), the project manager showed that farmers were very interested in production and cultural functions, with moderate compensatory power. NGOs focused on the conservation of biodiversity and cultural functions, armed with substantial conditioning power and expertise. Local business people were highly interested in dwelling and cultural functions, leveraging property ownership and management positions. Local public administration was interested in dwelling and cultural functions, using their management roles and expertise to implement policies. Academia focused on biodiversity conservation and cultural functions, influencing policy through expertise and charisma. Both the Forest Directorate and NARW emphasized biodiversity conservation, with NARW also interested in production, supported by their expertise and management positions.

The results presented in Tables 6–8 show a segregation of stakeholder categories that emerged based on their interest in the functions of the land. For instance, farmers, local business people, and investors in land prioritized economic functions (production, dwelling, and carrier), while entities such as CPA_Enviro, Academia, or NGOs were aligned with biodiversity conservation. In many situations, cultural functions occupied positions similar to those of biodiversity.

4.2. Beliefs of the project manager about the role of stakeholder analysis in their project

Table 9 summarizes the project manager's views on the role of stakeholder analysis in their projects. It highlights key themes and insights, along with illustrative quotes. Subsequently, we presented the main findings of the coordinate "Understand", offering nuanced insights derived from the data.

The following text presents the key findings on the themes identified in Table 9, providing detailed insights into the atmosphere characterization, stakeholder analysis, challenges, priority issues, and goldfish scenarios for the APU, BITransylv, and ApeBi projects.

i) Atmosphere characterization

Within the APU project, the atmosphere was positive, involving more than 111 people, although there were initial challenges in adapting to collaboration between participants. In the BITransylv project, the atmosphere was also positive, with favorable interactions mainly with local public authorities. Local public authorities exceeded the project manager's expectations in cooperation, demonstrating openness to both positive and negative aspects of biodiversity protection. Similarly, in the ApeBi project, the atmosphere was positive, team collaboration was good, and the partners showed interest in their activities. However, there was room for improvement, especially in fostering collaboration among all team members, as not everyone had the opportunity to work closely with everyone else, which might have affected the overall cohesion of the team. Also, a significant lack of information was observed among stakeholders, as reflected in their numerous public debates.

ii) Stakeholder Analysis

In the APU project, stakeholder analysis was not only considered but was also a separate and mandatory activity within the project. For the BITransylv project, stakeholder analysis was foreseen as an integral part of project management. In the ApeBi project, stakeholder analysis was found to be deficient. Despite efforts to identify and classify stakeholders, the analysis was rather superficial and was based on the opinion of the project team without directly involving stakeholders.

iii) Challenges in stakeholder analysis

In the APU project, the manager considered that the

Table 8
Levels of interest and power of the stakeholders in relation to land use functions in the ApeBi project (scores*).

Stakeholder category**	Interest				Power								
	Land function				Instruments of power			Sources of power					
	Production	Dwelling	Conservation of biodiversity	Cultural	Carrier*** (transportation, industrial sites)	Coercive power***	Compensatory power***	Conditioning power***	Charisma***	Property (goods)	Expertise	Management position in a company/institution membership in an NGO, church, or association)	Family/Peers
Farmers	3	2	1	3	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1
NGOs	1	1	3	3	1	1	1	3	3	1	3	1	1
Local business people	2	3	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	1
Local public administration	2	3	2	3	3	3	3	1	2	1	3	3	1
Academia	1	1	3	3	1	1	1	3	2	1	3	1	1
Land investors	2	3	1	2	3	1	2	1	1	3	2	1	1
CPA_Enviro	1	1	3	2	2	3	1	1	1	1	3	3	1
Forest Directorate	3	1	2	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	3	3	1
NARW	2	1	2	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	3	3	1

* Scores are measured on a scale of 1–3 (1 = Low/insignificant, 2 = Moderate, 3 = High).

** Please refer to the legend of Fig. 2 for the abbreviations of stakeholders' categories.

*** The definition of these terms is included in Table 2.

Table 9
Synthesis of coding results for the “Understand” coordinate [Questions 6 (points 6.1–6.6) from the interview script, Annex 1].

Deductive coding			Inductive coding		
Main codes (pre-established codes)					
Code no.	Code definition	Direct quotes (examples) associated with inductive coding	Code number	Code definition	Direct quotes (examples) associated with inductive coding
(6.1)	Atmosphere characterization (code name adapted after Aaltonen, 2011 : “Project stakeholder environment”)	“(…) at the beginning, it was more difficult; some knew each other very well, while others did not. It took some time before they started to collaborate. I think there were more than 100 people involved, but the atmosphere was good, and we worked well until the end.” (APU_PM)	6.1.a	Interdisciplinary challenges	BITransylv “The interdisciplinary nature of the project required finding a middle ground to reconcile the perspectives of biologists and foresters.” (BITransylv_PM)
				Lack of interest	“(…) we participated in many public debates, and there was a major lack of information among stakeholders. They didn’t read anything and didn’t inform themselves. They were not interested in the studies we conducted or what we said. Each came only with their interests” (ApeBi_PM).
(6.2)	Stakeholder analysis performed (code name adapted after Aaltonen, 2011 : “Project stakeholder analysis”)	“I attended all the meetings with stakeholders, which I believe were around 30. This project did not have a distinct activity focused on a thorough stakeholder analysis. We made some tables listing the stakeholders and their interests in the project, but it wasn’t done in-depth. It was more based on our opinions, without engaging in extensive conversations with them. The meetings were mainly to present the proposed measures and to hear their feedback.” (ApeBi_PM)	6.2.a	Partial stakeholder analysis	“A distinct activity involved the analysis of stakeholders, although not in a comprehensive way.” (ApeBi_PM)
(6.3)	Challenges in stakeholder analysis (adapted after “Critical and unexpected incidents during the project”, Annex A from Aaltonen, 2011)	“There are certain areas with strict protection, where only traditional activities such as herding or sustainable wood exploitation are allowed.” (APU_PM) “Ideally, the project should be designed with stakeholders, but this rarely happens in practice, making it the most challenging aspect. If you succeed in gathering everyone for a meeting before starting the project, you can establish objectives and activities more effectively. Generally, I’ve noticed that stakeholders are absent during these initial goal-setting stages. Therefore, project management and planning often proceed without their input, requiring the project manager and the management team to speculate on their requirements and interests. Ideally, all these aspects should be decided together with stakeholders.” (BITransylv_PM) “Those involved in project management must theoretically consider the interests and needs of stakeholders. However, when the management team confronts reality, how do they rectify what they have outlined in the project with the actual needs on the ground? How do they address situations where they did not accurately anticipate the needs of stakeholders? In our case, we could anticipate these stakeholder needs because of our experience with other similar projects.” (BITransylv_PM). “I think stakeholder analysis in biodiversity projects is deficient.” (ApeBi_PM)	6.3.a	Opposition	“People in the area think these programs put too many limits and restrictions on them, which is a big problem in getting all stakeholders involved.” (APU_PM)
			6.3.b	Coordination	“The most challenging, I believe, is to succeed in reaching them after the initial contact, finding a day when everyone can meet, organizing a meeting involving all stakeholders, and finding a time when each is available to attend the project’s opening, closing or even during its implementation.” (BITransylv_PM)
			6.3.c	Engagement	“We didn’t fully understand their perspective (of stakeholders). We identified stakeholders based on how we thought they might be, relying on our previous experiences with them. We did not engage in individual discussions to truly understand what they understood.” (ApeBi_PM)
(6.4)	Retrospective assessment	Each project has performed a stakeholder analysis in some form or another. Therefore,			“No answer was requested for this part.
(6.5)	Priority issues (adapted after Appendix A, “A.2. Project background”, the 10th question from Aaltonen, 2011)	“(…) More attention should be paid to the human factor, especially local communities. Information and awareness activities are necessary not only related to the exploitation and conservation of resources but also to the	6.5.a	Information	“When well informed, the human factor becomes a key player in biodiversity. Leave it undisturbed may not suffice; instead, it requires our involvement through information and support, not just for exploitation, but for maintaining and

(continued on next page)

Table 9 (continued)

Deductive coding		Inductive coding	
Main codes (pre-established codes)			
	promotion of certain facilities, such as tourism in those areas." (APU_PM)		promoting these natural resources, especially in the context of tourism-related opportunities in the respective areas." (APU_PM)
(6.6).	Goldfish scenario (authors' contribution)	6.6.a	Time constraints
	"I would like us in all these projects to focus more on (environmental) studies and less on paperwork. That's the only thing I can say, and people should understand the perspective of other people, not just pursue their interests" (ApeBi_PM).		"Unfortunately, the project ran for only a year and a half, which is quite short, but that was the time allocation in the project. The project started with a delay (...) So, above all, I would like at least a doubling of this period." (APU_PM)"
		6.6.b	Governance structure
			"(...) the administration of protected areas should no longer be done by the National Agency for Protected Natural Areas; instead, these protected areas should be assigned to NGOs or academic institutions because it was much better back then." (BITransylv_PM)
		6.6.c	Bureaucracy
			"I would like to be able to focus more on studies and less on paperwork in all these projects." (ApeBi_PM)
		6.6.d	Empathy
			ApeBi "(...) and for people to understand, to look at and act from the other's perspective, and not exclusively focus on their interests." (ApeBi_PM)

* The code number is associated with the questions from the interview script (Annex 1).

relationship with the local community requires increased attention, as illustrated by locals who prepared petitions to be excluded from the protected area. The management of the relationship with the local community posed the main challenge in the stakeholder analysis, given the introduction of some restrictions in the protected area. APU_PM commented. A significant challenge in the BITransylv project was the stakeholders' limited participation during the initial stages. Ideally, the project should be co-designed with stakeholders to establish objectives and activities effectively. However, stakeholders were often absent during these critical goal-setting stages, leaving the project manager and team to speculate on their requirements and interests. Additionally, coordinating meeting schedules was a major challenge, as it was difficult to find a time when all stakeholders could attend the opening, closing, or even during its implementation. The project manager noted that gathering all participants for a meeting before launching the project would significantly improve the planning process. Moreover, the BITransylv project presented challenges in the relationship with the Forestry Directorate, which had dual interests in biodiversity conservation and timber exploitation. The interdisciplinary nature of the project required finding a middle ground to reconcile the perspectives of biologists and foresters. This was the main opposition throughout the project, but ultimately, common ground was achieved.

In the ApeBi project, the main challenge was the superficial understanding of stakeholders' perspectives. The project team identified stakeholders based on their assumptions and previous experiences without engaging in individual discussions to truly understand the stakeholders' views. This lack of direct engagement resulted in a disconnect between the project team's perceptions and the actual needs and understanding of the stakeholders. The project manager admitted they did not fully grasp the stakeholders' perspectives.

iv) Priority issues

APU_PM highlighted the need to pay greater attention to the human factor. Informational and awareness activities were considered essential to educate residents about the exploitation and conservation of

resources. Furthermore, promoting facilities such as tourism in the area was identified as crucial. The manager stressed that a well-informed human factor is key to biodiversity conservation. Simply leaving these communities undisturbed is not sufficient; instead, proactive involvement through information and support is necessary to protect nature, especially about tourism opportunities. Taking into account the dual interests of the Forestry Directorate and its relationship with other stakeholders, BITransylv_PM pleaded for more significant ecological consideration and collaboration between the Forestry Directorate, ecologists, and biologists, emphasizing the need for a common language and shared understanding between ecologists and foresters. He believed that addressing epistemological and conceptual disparities at the academic and scientific levels would be crucial to fostering better collaboration. ApeBi_PM believed that closer involvement of members of Academia in the realities of the project would contribute to the success of Natura 2000 projects.

v) Goldfish scenario

In the APU project, the need for a more extended timeframe to accurately assess the status of species and habitats was highlighted. The ideal scenario for BITransylv_PM involved the collaborative conceptualization of the project with stakeholders because practical challenges often arise when stakeholders are absent while establishing project objectives and activities. Another wish was to change the authority in charge of the protected area, in particular, to shift from the National Agency for Protected Natural Areas (NAPNA) to the custody of NGOs or academic institutions for more effective conservation (which were responsible for the administration of protected areas in the past). In the ApeBi project, the manager emphasized the need to address the bureaucratic workload, document preparation at the expense of fieldwork, and the importance of people understanding and looking at things from the perspectives of each other, not solely pursuing their interests.

4.3. Overview of results across projects

We illustrated the relationships between stakeholders in Fig. 3 by conducting a thematic analysis of the responses to questions 2–5 (questions associated with the coordinate "Prioritize", see Table 1, column 2, and Annex 1) and incorporating the information from the ALM tables (refer to Annex 2). Fig. 3 presents more conflictual relationships

Fig. 3. Integrative attribute of Natura 2000 projects. (Please refer to the legend of Fig. 2 for the abbreviations of stakeholders' categories).

compared to Table 5. This is attributed to the inclusion of the results of the thematic analysis (responses to questions 2–5) and the ALM results presented in Table 5. We highlighted in green several main cooperation and complementarity relations between stakeholders and in red the conflictual relationships (Fig. 3). While the former category can enhance the integrative character, the latter fragilizes it.

A graphical representation of the results for capability-responsiveness, sustainability mindset, and power equilibrium is included in Tables 10 and 11. An aggregate score for all items of the capability-responsiveness for each stakeholder is reported in Table 11. The interest of stakeholders in land functions (as perceived by project managers) highlights the presence or absence of the premises of the

Table 10

Land function evaluation (average for all projects) and stakeholders' sustainability mindset, according to project managers' perceptions.

Stakeholders category	Economic ^a	Biodiversity ^a	Cultural ^a	Average interest ^b	Reversed average interest ^c	Distance Economic-Biodiversity ^d	Distance Economic-Cultural ^d	Distance Biodiversity-Cultural ^d	Average distance	Sustainability mindset ^e
NGOs	1	3	3	2.3	1.7	2	2	0	1.3	1.5
CPA_Enviro	1.7	3	2	2.2	1.8	1.3	0.3	1	0.9	1.3
Academia	1	3	2.7	2.2	1.8	2	1.7	0.3	1.3	1.6
Pre-university edu. institutions	2.3	2	3	2.4	1.6	0.3	0.7	1	0.7	1.1
Local public admin	2.9	2	3	2.6	1.4	0.9	0.1	1	0.7	1.0
Forest Directorate	2	2	1	1.7	2.3	0	1	1	0.7	1.5
NARW	1.5	2	1	1.5	2.5	0.5	0.5	1	0.7	1.6
NRIAC	2	1	1	1.3	2.7	1	1	0	0.7	1.7
Local business people	2.4	1	1.7	1.7	2.3	1.4	0.7	0.7	0.9	1.6
Local community	3	1	1	1.7	2.3	2	2	0	1.3	1.8
Land investors	2.7	1	2	1.9	2.1	1.7	0.7	1	1.1	1.6
CPA_Agri	2.3	1	1	1.4	2.6	1.3	1.3	0	0.9	1.7
Farmers	2.6	1	2.3	2.0	2.0	1.6	0.3	1.3	1.1	1.6
Average	2.1	1.8	1.9			1.2	0.9	0.6		

^a Calculate as the average of the production, dwelling, and carrier functions in all projects (values from Tables 6–8; e.g., for farmers: (3 + 3 + 2 + 3 + 3 + 2 + 3 + 2 + 2) / 9 = 2.6; The scores are calculated on the scale of 1–3 (1 = Low/insignificant, 2 = Moderate, 3 = High).].

^b Calculated as the average of the interests in the previous three columns [e.g., for NGOs: (1 + 3 + 3) / 3 = 2.3]

^c Reversed average interest = 1 + max value of average interest – current average interest (the max value of average interest is 3).

^d Absolute value.

^e Sustainability mindset = (Reversed average interest + Average distance) / 2

Table 11
Cross-project results for capability-responsiveness, sustainability mindset premises, and power.

Stakeholder category ¹	Capability-responsiveness ²	Interests in land functions as premises for a sustainability mindset ³ (average scores for all projects) ⁶	Power			
			The dominant type of power ⁴ (the dominant power type, considering all projects; average score) ⁶		The dominant source of power ⁵ (the dominant power source, considering all projects; average score) ⁶	
NGOs	16.3 ⚡		3		3	
CPA_Enviro	15.6 ⚡		2.3		2.3 2.3	
Academia	14.3 ⚡		2.7		3	
Pre-university edu. institutions	14 ⚡		3		3	
Local public admin	13.3 ⚡		2.3		2.7	
Forest Directorate	12.5 ⚡		2.5		2.5 2.5	
NARW	12.5 ⚡		2.5		2.5 2.5	
NRIAC	10 ⚡		2		2 2	
Local business people	10 ⚡		2		2.3	
Local community	10 ⚡		1	1	1	3
Land investors	9 ⚡		2.5		2.5	
CPA_Agri	9 ⚡		3		3 3	
Farmers	8.6 ⚡		1.7		2	

Legend:

- Please refer to the legend of Figure 2 for the abbreviations of stakeholders' categories
- ⚡ The scores represent the average total scores for capability-responsiveness of each stakeholder category calculated in Table 4. The scores can range from 6 to 18.
- Interest in the Economic land functions (Production, Dwelling, and Carrier functions).
 Interest in the Biodiversity land function.
 Interest in the Cultural land function.
- Coercive power; Compensatory power; Conditioning power
- Charisma; Property (goods, money); Expertise; Management position in a company /institution and/ or membership in an NGO, church, association, etc.; Family, friends
- We calculated the overall average for all projects. This was calculated by summing the scores obtained in each project for a specific stakeholder category, for each type of interest/ type of power/ source of power, and then dividing the sum by the number of occurrences in all projects. The scores can range from 1 to 3.

sustainability mindset on land functions. Two components were considered in assessing the sustainability mindset regarding land functions: the average interest in land functions (its reversed form) and the average distance between land functions. The reversed form of the

average interest was used in the calculation of the sustainability mindset because a lower value indicates an increased sustainability mindset, such as the meaning of the average distance between land functions. We considered that the sustainability mindset should assign (almost) equal

importance to all land functions, and the importance should be high (Tables 10 and 11). We took the mid-point of both sustainability mindset components as the level acceptable for considering that a sustainability mindset is present. Thus, for the evaluation of the interest in land functions, we thought that interest is sustainable if its reversed average value was equal to or below 2 (its values can range from 1 to 3); for the average distance, its value should be equal to or below 1 (its values can range from 0 to 2). On the basis of these levels, on average, there is a sustainability mindset if the calculated value is equal to or below 1.5 $[(2 + 1)/2 = 1.5]$. Power equilibrium encompasses the types of power and their sources in the hands of stakeholders, and it is relevant for fostering inclusive and just societies. Thus, power should be managed to prevent the concentration of influence that disadvantages certain stakeholders and ensures a more balanced decision-making process in Natura 2000 projects.

5. Discussion. Cross-projects analysis

5.1. Stakeholders' power, interests, capability-responsiveness, and the integrative character of Natura 2000 projects

The characteristics and interactions of stakeholders are acknowledged as powerful elements in the development and sustainability of the system (Bryson, 2004). Therefore, the analytical process that investigates the diverse interests and power among stakeholders is vital in guiding and informing the agenda for transformative change.

The results of this study offer information to unlock the transformative potential of Natura 2000 projects from the perspective of stakeholder analysis. One objective of transformative change is to assess participants involved in decision-making processes critically (Pascual et al., 2022), leading to reshaping existing institutional systems. In pursuit of this objective, conducting stakeholder analysis becomes crucial.

The power-interest matrix provided valuable insights, demonstrating variability across Natura 2000 projects where stakeholder categories were positioned differently depending on the project context. This variability underscores the need for an adaptable and customized approach tailored to the specifics of each case. For example, the characterization of stakeholders in two of the analyzed projects highlighted farmers positioned along the high-interest-low-power axis. This placement highlights their significant stake in project outcomes and indicates their limited authority in influencing decision-making processes. This disparity emphasizes the importance of recognizing and addressing nuances in stakeholder dynamics to effectively manage project engagement and outcomes. This finding casts light on the need for empowerment measures for farmers. Similarly, Gerritsen (2012), who examined the usefulness of the biodiversity concept in populated protected areas in western Mexico, argues that conservation activities in protected areas should include consideration of farmers' perspectives to better address conservation aspects. One possibility is the implementation of procedures that allow them to participate in the decisions that affect their interests. In New Zealand, stakeholder participation in setting biodiversity priorities for agricultural landscapes was facilitated through three pathways for engagement involving public, private, and civic sectors (MacLeod et al., 2022).

Conversely, representatives of public authorities were placed on the high-power-high-interest axis, showcasing their significant power and interest in the projects. We can observe that the potential for conflicts arises from the notable power disparity between farmers and public authorities, since the latter group holds control of decision-making. Research on understanding differences in agrarian reforms in developing countries over time suggests that efficiency-reducing outcomes in these policies can detrimentally affect farmers who lack political representation or power (Binswanger and Deininger, 1997). This underscores the critical impact of power differentials in shaping agricultural policies and outcomes. Such inequality can lead to tensions

and conflicts, mainly if farmers' interests and perspectives are not adequately considered in decision-making processes. The scores for the level of capability responsiveness further confirmed this result.

The notable discrepancy in the capability-responsiveness scores (Table 4) highlights a potential disparity in the effectiveness of stakeholder engagement within the Natura 2000 projects. Thus, NGOs and CPA_Enviro consistently achieve top positions, while farmers rank the lowest, indicating a significant imbalance. As suggested by Menconi et al. (2017), farmers are often considered only as a source of information in participatory processes, requiring greater empowerment for effective rural appraisal. Higher average scores for public administrative authorities, including CPA_Enviro, NARW, the Forest Directorate, and local public authorities, further emphasize this point. These groups appear to have better engagement and capability-responsiveness compared to farmers and the local community. This imbalance raises concerns about the inclusivity and equity of stakeholder engagement processes. It suggests a need to re-evaluate and potentially redesign these processes to ensure that the voices of those living in and directly impacted by the project outcomes are heard.

We remark that public administrative authorities are perceived to have more capability-responsiveness compared to individual farmers and local communities. This power asymmetry can lead to disparity in influencing project outcomes. However, it is evident that addressing natural resource management requires multi-party collaboration between public authorities, private businesses, experts, or communities, considering the local dimension (Bouwen and Taillieu, 2004). Practical implementation of such collaboration is challenging due to the difficulties of reconciling disparate objectives, such as those linked to individual rights, equality, or the sustainable use of finite resources within the same decision-making framework (Kyllönen et al., 2006).

Slight differences appeared between the analyzed projects regarding stakeholder inclusion in the power-interest matrix, which reflects the particularities of each case. For example, in two projects, farmers were assigned high interest, and in one, low interest, highlighting the variability in stakeholder priorities and engagement across different contexts. Similar disparities between stakeholders in five Mediterranean regions were illustrated by Moreira et al. (2019), underscoring the need for strategies to address their interests effectively.

Similarly, NGOs may have more knowledge and responsiveness than individual farmers and local communities, contributing to a power imbalance. The result is even more concerning as Fig. 3 highlights conflicting relationships between NGOs and farmers or CPA_Enviro and farmers. Similarly, in the Czech Republic, Meierová (2020) highlighted that farmers frequently characterized NGOs in casual interviews as deterrent agents that impeded progress and disrupted their daily agricultural routines. According to a report from the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) cited by Tan (2005), evaluating the impact of NGOs in conflict resolution is a complex task. However, the report advises against hastily diminishing the perceived strengths of NGOs. Furthermore, it underlines that when NGOs bring aid and resources into conflict situations, these contributions often become an added source of struggle and disagreement among the conflicting parties (Tan, 2005).

Fig. 3 shows a network of conflictual relationships between stakeholders that could threaten the integrative character of collaborative efforts. ApeBi_PM explained that the conflicts were rooted in stakeholders' narrow and unidimensional understanding of Natura 2000 sites, considering only their interests. They did not understand or deliberately ignored that Natura 2000 is a complex system with multiple stakeholders with different needs and characteristics.

While the relationship between farmers and public authorities, in general, is perceived as conflictual, in the APU project, the partnership between the farmers and CPA_Agri is explained by APU_PM in light of the subsidies farmers receive from CPA_Agri. In ApeBi, the conflictual relationship between the mayor and CPA_Enviro is evident, as municipalities disagree with establishing protected areas within their

territories, citing a lack of consultation and viewing these areas as obstacles to development that increase their environmental study costs. Similarly, [Castro and Nielsen \(2001\)](#) warn that communities and local authorities may find themselves tasked with the responsibilities and expenses of resource management, lacking any substantial delegation of power or involvement in decision-making processes, a phenomenon called by [Anderson \(2000\)](#) “decentralization without empowerment”.

NGOs have a predominant interest in biodiversity conservation and cultural function and have one of the most conflictual positions. This finding indicates challenges in harmonizing NGOs’ objectives with the stakeholders. On the contrary, Academia, with a predominant focus on biodiversity, takes a contrasting stance, being involved in only two conflicting relationships. [Watt et al. \(2003\)](#) considered that scientists are often in a challenging position, as they are required to fulfill multiple roles, from a source of information for stakeholders to mediators. Despite this, the role of scientists in conflict resolution is acknowledged. For example, [Henle et al. \(2008\)](#) offer some examples where scientists’ participation was crucial in managing agricultural land for biodiversity, as often there is no guarantee that planned management strategies will not have adverse consequences. A study on the conflict management style of experts (for biodiversity conservation projects) in Romania showed that the style of experts was predominantly integrative ([Petrescu-Mag et al., 2024b](#)). This style is characterized by the fact that the person using it makes efforts to create solutions that satisfy the needs of all, hence being suitable for conflicts such as those related to Natura 2000 projects, where the collaboration of all stakeholders is essential for project success. It has been demonstrated that developing effective conflict resolution solutions depends on understanding the characteristics of stakeholders, including their conflict behavior (e.g., their conflict management style) ([Beverland et al., 2010](#)), which in turn is influenced by their needs, attitude, power, etc. Furthermore, becoming aware of the various types of conflict behavior enables participants to gain insight into their actions and interpret the behaviors of others more constructively using feedback ([Broukhim et al., 2019](#); [Shell, 2001](#)). Considering these, we can value Academia as a potential mediator or facilitator in Natura 2000 project conflict situations because of its impartiality, competence, and ability to bridge disparate viewpoints.

5.2. Power equilibrium in Natura 2000 projects

In this study, conditioning power is the dominant type of power encountered most frequently among stakeholders (used in 50 % of cases, [Table 11](#)). This can signal the existence of good negotiation abilities because it involves a more complex exchange of offers and requests between partners compared to the other power types. Negotiation is a valuable tool. Used constructively, negotiation can solve conflicts, integrate different and similar interests into a commonly agreed solution, and create value starting from initially divergent positions ([Barrot, 2007](#)). Furthermore, conditioning power is usually preferred by environmentalists because they aim to change the system of values that influences behavior; in opposition, coercive or compensatory power usually triggers compliance ([Santopietro, 1995](#)). Values are desirables, abstract goals that affect decisions, choices, and behavior, serving as guidelines in serve as guidelines in a person’s life ([Schwartz, 1992](#)). Both genetics [through the biological infrastructure (e.g., brain processes) that influence the preference of specific values over others] and environmental factors influence the value system ([Twito and Knafo-Noam, 2020](#)). Of course, the use of conditioning power is one of a multitude of factors [e.g., social change, demographics ([Manago, 2014](#)), religious and spiritual shifts ([Singleton, 2014](#)), and social networks ([Mukta et al., 2019](#))] that can influence values. Conditioning power can be more effective than coercive and rewarding powers in changing people’s values because it operates through deeper mechanisms that contribute to value change, such as internalization of values and education ([Clayton and Myers, 2015](#)), use of cultural and social norms ([Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002](#)), and stimulation of long-term commitment ([Nisbet](#)

and [Gick, 2008](#)).

Expertise, management position, and membership in a particular organization are the sources of power most frequently nominated by project managers as being dominant and used the most frequently (in 44 % and 33 % of cases, respectively, [Table 11](#)). It can be inferred that these power sources were available and/or effective for the stakeholders who used them. This means that requests for compliance or change were more easily accepted when they were made by people perceived to have expertise in the matter and management position than when they were connected to money, charisma, family, and friends. Similarly, [Lines \(2007\)](#) found that expertise relevant to project objectives and position positively influence implementation success (in a project for the transformation of a large telecommunications company). Furthermore, the resources available to influence project outcomes were more abundant through the management position or membership in an organization for the stakeholders who used them compared to the other power sources (e.g., they had the power to allocate resources, influence decisions, etc.). Revealing a stakeholder’s preferred power type and source suggests efficient ways to communicate and connect to that stakeholder, increasing the chances of cooperation for project success.

Transformative changes restructure the existing power dynamics ([Arias-Arévalo et al., 2123](#)), altering the existing *status quo*, in the present case, within Natura 2000 projects. Many conflictual situations within the analyzed projects signal the need for change. This may include better use of the information regarding stakeholders’ power type and sources and increasing stakeholders’ flexibility in adapting them to better respond to conflictual situations. However, it should be considered that nature protection areas are very complex systems and, consequently, the conflicts present there are usually also intricate due to, for example, complex and uncertain knowledge, divergent perspectives among multiple resource users, and distrust between the users and other stakeholders ([Kyllönen et al., 2006](#)). Moreover, not all conflicts are the same. Conflicts can be constructive when they involve efforts to address or resolve incompatibilities between groups, or destructive, when they aim to undermine or harm the opposing party ([Fisher and Rucki, 2017](#)) citing ([Nowak et al., 2012](#)). Therefore, constructive conflicts drive innovation and adaptive capacity, promoting continuous improvement, while destructive conflicts undermine the resilience and sustainability of the system, indicating areas where intervention may be needed. Furthermore, depending on the impact (little importance or a low level of magnitude) that a conflict can have, there can be neutral or minor conflicts that may not require action ([Jehn, 1997](#)).

To effectively address conflicts, it is essential to regard conflict management as an integral part of ongoing co-management practices of resource use rather than as a separate phase dedicated to conflict resolution ([Kyllönen et al., 2006](#)). Managing and solving conflicts is crucial for sustainable environmental governance and human development ([Fisher and Rucki, 2017](#)). Elements of a successful conflict management process in Natura 2000 areas can include (but are not limited to): tackling knowledge and perspective issues to initiate a learning process; creating sub-processes that foster mutual trust between all parties (including the managing authority or a third party); defining explicit roles and clear entitlements for the parties; and offering a credible alternative for cooperation that influences the parties’ payoff assessments throughout the process ([Kyllönen et al., 2006](#)).

Although there is a direct link between conflict and sustainability – since sustainability requires making explicit choices about prioritizing needs and addressing them, which often leads to conflicts among groups with competing or incompatible interests ([Fisher and Rucki, 2017](#)) – conflicts are not the only aspects that must be addressed when pursuing transformative change toward more sustainable systems. Many other components should be considered, including the opposed situation to a conflict, namely cooperation. Complementarity and cooperation can also have a dual nature in regards to their transformative potential (or non-potential), resulting in positive cooperation when strong cooperation between stakeholders leads to significant transformative outcomes

(de Koning et al., 2023; Nowak, 2012; Velten et al., 2021), and negative cooperation, when cooperation among powerful stakeholders leads to the entrenchment of the status quo, thereby hindering the transformative potential (Alrøe and Noe, 2016); additionally, cooperation without coordination can also decrease the effect of the former (Gulati et al., 2012).

5.3. Sustainability mindset

The analysis of stakeholder perceptions reveals that (according to the project managers) most stakeholder categories tend to assign balanced importance to the three types of land functions – economic, biodiversity, and cultural. This balanced approach suggests that the stakeholders recognize the multifaceted role these functions play in land management and development. However, most of this group consistently rated the importance of these land functions as relatively low. This pattern indicates a potential challenge in fostering a sustainability mindset among stakeholders. The lower average importance ratings may reflect a lack of engagement or prioritization of land functions, which could undermine efforts to promote sustainable practices. As Grilli and Curtis (2021) argue, reduced interest in essential land functions can impede sustainable behavior and decision-making.

Although two stakeholder groups (NGOs and Academia) had a relatively high average interest in land functions, they did not qualify for a sustainability mindset due to the disparity between the interest in various land functions (average distance above the 1-point limit). This means they care less about one of the land functions, signaling the need to increase their interest in that direction. On average, local public administration has the most sustainability mindset of all groups, making them reliable partners in implementing Natura 2000 projects.

Despite the relevance of the average results, it is important to consider the specific features of each case. For example, APU_PM's experience with local administration was not ideal. Cross-project results showed that the local community had the lowest sustainability mindset, increasing the challenge of collaborating with them on the projects. Most stakeholder groups (seven out of twelve) did not show a sustainability mindset. The concern for their interests and ignorance of other land functions highlights the need for efforts to conciliate stakeholders' conflicting interests. The BITransylv_PM confirms this result, considering that land investors view protected areas as obstacles due to restrictions on land acquisition and use. The analysis of stakeholders' sustainability mindset is important because it signals where to intervene to change their mindset towards sustainability, a condition for the achievement of Natura 2000 objectives. The sustainability mindset recognizes the interconnected nature of economic, biodiversity, and cultural interests in land functions. It can unlock transformative potential by inspiring integrated planning, ecosystem-based management, green economic initiatives, and cultural heritage preservation. This holistic approach addresses the complexity of land use challenges and drives positive, lasting changes that benefit present and future generations.

5.4. Reflect to transform

The present study showed that managing protected areas is frequently challenging due to competing interests between various stakeholders. Several recommendations from project managers' main recurring ideas are synthesized as follows.

1. The stakeholder analysis should not follow a standardized model. It is not a "one size fits all" and should consider the particularities of each project. ApeBi_PM nicely voices this: "... meetings with stakeholders and everything you do to communicate project results, which is mandatory to do, have no efficiency whatsoever and produce almost no change because everything unfolds quite standard."

2. Inclusive language in stakeholder analysis to prevent power imbalances and promote inclusiveness is very important: "Experts speak quite sophisticatedly, while the farmers and locals feel intimidated. How can I speak after this lady has spoken so beautifully? So, either they become aggressive or say nothing, and then you end up with nothing from these stakeholder meetings." (ApeBi_PM).
3. The need for an integrative approach within Natura 2000 projects: "... if I were to change something in these projects (Natura 2000 projects), I would include other studies in addition to biodiversity; the focus should also be on communities, on people." (ApeBi_PM).

Moreover, several practical implications derived from the findings can contribute to the transformative change process within Natura 2000 projects management: *i) To empower communities*: Opportunities for capacity-building and knowledge and information acquisition needed for meaningful participation should be created; *ii) To reduce power disparity*: Creation of collaborative (co-management) decision-making structures and processes to facilitate power-sharing among stakeholders; and, *iii) To foster inclusive stakeholder engagement*: An inclusive environment must be created that values different perspectives and ensures that all stakeholders have a seat at the table.

5.5. Limitations, future research directions, and relevance for other countries

Due to the unique characteristics of each Natura 2000 project, the generalizability of the results is limited. The answers to the exploratory questions are based on the project managers' perceptions. Previous studies identified both convergence and divergence between the views of different stakeholder categories (Veisi et al., 2022; Daher et al., 2020). Hence, investigating other stakeholders' perspectives in a future research direction can provide a more holistic understanding of the system. Stakeholder interactions are multifaceted, and research may not capture the full complexity of relationships, especially considering the interconnectedness of various stakeholders. Although the study includes recommendations for transformative change, it may not encompass all potential factors influencing Natura 2000 projects, and the proposed solutions are not exhaustive. Future studies could integrate multidisciplinary approaches involving ecology, sociology, economics, and governance. This holistic perspective can enhance understanding of the interrelated factors influencing the success of Natura 2000 projects. Furthermore, future studies could compare the current results with similar research on Natura 2000 projects within Romania and internationally to identify any deviations and explore their contextual explanations. Such comparisons will offer valuable insights for practitioners in protected area management.

Despite limitations, research on Natura 2000 projects can have far-reaching implications internationally by informing policies, fostering collaboration, and contributing to global efforts towards biodiversity conservation and sustainable development. Despite the lack of generalizability, this research provides critical insight into the challenges faced by protected areas globally. These insights can be applied in several ways. First, these case studies serve as concrete examples that can be used to raise awareness among policymakers, conservationists, the general public, and other stakeholders about the complex dynamics (such as interests, power, and conflicts) within protected areas, highlighting the need for nuanced and context-specific approaches to conservation. At the same time, the results of these Natura 2000 projects can identify common challenges stakeholders face in other regions. Second, by identifying different stakeholders' specific interests, power, and roles, this research can inform and strengthen advocacy efforts, promoting increased international cooperation and commitment to conservation initiatives. Enhanced stakeholder understanding can lead to more effective collaboration and resource allocation, ensuring that conservation strategies are not only comprehensive but also inclusive. Third, understanding the power structures of stakeholders and their

dynamics can contribute to developing more informed, equitable, and targeted policies, particularly for Natura 2000 projects. Policies can incorporate mechanisms for regular monitoring and adaptation, using the lessons learned from these protected areas to inform adjustments and improvements. They can be continuously improved based on ongoing learning and feedback from specific cases. When policies can be tailored to address the unique challenges and opportunities within each protected area, they can ultimately lead to more sustainable and resilient conservation outcomes.

6. Conclusions

Despite the positive perception of the atmosphere in each project, a network of conflictual relationships undermines the integrative character of the analyzed projects. Academia stands out as a potential actor that can mediate relations between participants. This indicates that one recognizes the need for a neutral and knowledgeable entity to facilitate conflict resolution. While neutrality and knowledge are crucial, it is important to consider that these qualities alone may not suffice. Empathy and facilitation skills are equally vital in navigating the complexities of conflicts. Additionally, despite their knowledge, experts can sometimes be biased or lack an interdisciplinary perspective. Given the difficulty for one person to embody all these qualities, it is advisable to utilize a team approach, if possible. A team can bring together diverse skills and perspectives, enhancing the effectiveness of the conflict resolution process. Moreover, project managers' views on stakeholder analysis could impact subsequent stakeholder management and overall project management. These views shape the identification and prioritization of stakeholders, influencing engagement strategies, conflict resolution methods, and resource allocation. Consequently, these factors affect the project's transformation potential by determining how well stakeholder needs and concerns are addressed throughout the project lifecycle. To mitigate these risks, assembling a diverse team, providing bias awareness training, developing a robust stakeholder engagement framework, and implementing regular reviews and feedback are essential. Encouraging cross-functional collaboration, establishing monitoring and evaluation mechanisms, maintaining transparent communication, and equipping team members with conflict resolution training will further enhance the effectiveness of stakeholder management and project outcomes.

The degree of capability-responsiveness is somewhat polarized, with public authorities and NGOs generally being more knowledgeable than farmers, indicating a power asymmetry. This raises concerns about the equitable distribution of resources and can generate support for an uneven distribution of influence, which could lead to a power imbalance that, in turn, may affect the engagement and success of various stakeholders. Finally, stakeholders appear to be segregated based on their interests in land functions. Those primarily interested in economic land functions (farmers, local business people, land investors, local

community) tend to prioritize biodiversity conservation interests less. This segregation could potentially lead to conflicts with stakeholders like CPA_Enviro, NGOs, or NARW, and it's crucial to address these issues to ensure a harmonious project environment.

An overarching conclusion is that achieving win-win solutions and transformative change toward adequate nature protection in Natura 2000 projects is a complex task. It requires a deep understanding of stakeholders' diverse perspectives and interests. To enhance the effectiveness of protected areas management, it's crucial to navigate these conflicting interests by fostering collaboration and addressing the varied needs of stakeholders. Moreover, recognizing the ever-changing nature of stakeholder relations and adjusting management strategies is essential to balance biodiversity conservation goals and the interests of those reliant on the resources of protected areas.

Author Statement

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Macicasan Vlad: Investigation, Data curation. **Hartel Tibor:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Reti Kinga Olga:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Petrescu-Mag Ruxandra Malina:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Petrescu Dacia Crina:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Badarau Alexandru Sabin:** Investigation, Data curation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Annex 1. Interview script

Hello! Thank you for agreeing to spend the next hour and a half answering a few questions about one of the Natura 2000 projects you participated in as project manager. Could you provide details about this project (e.g., project name, objectives, outcomes)?

1) Based on the scientific literature dedicated to the role of stakeholders in decision-making regarding land use and the information provided by the Cămpia Transilvaniei Local Action Group website, we have identified the following categories of stakeholders regarding land use in Transylvania.

Considering your experience in managing projects implemented in Transylvania, **please tell us which category of stakeholders should NOT be in the list below and if you believe that we should add another category.** Additionally, if you think that representatives of a particular category should be analyzed separately (e.g., Romgaz should be investigated separately from the local business people), please mention this and provide your reasoning. Thank you!

■ Farmers (Civil Society)

⊙ NGOs (Civil Society)

◆ Local business community: agricultural companies, tourism companies, trade companies, furniture companies, Romgaz company (even if it is with the participation of the Romanian state)

- Public local administration
- ♣ Academia (universities, researchers)

x x x
x x x
x x x

Land investors

- Central administration
- ▼ Other categories...

2) Please include the stakeholders identified above in one of the four categories below. Consider their Power to influence project development and their Interest in the project.

[The power-interest matrix below]

3) Please attach a number from 1–3 to the stakeholders in the matrix from question number 2, indicating the level of knowledge of others, interaction, attitude, etc., where:

a) **Knowledge of others = Level of knowledge about the other parties involved**

Now, let us recall the activities undertaken in the project you participated in as project manager. How would you characterize the level of knowledge of each category of stakeholders with respect to responsibilities, roles, and obligations that other stakeholders have? For example, what is the level of knowledge of civil society representatives on the responsibilities, roles, and obligations of local public administration? Try to quantify this level of knowledge from 1 to 3, where 1 =No/Minimum level of knowledge, 2 = Average level of knowledge, 3 =Complete knowledge level of knowledge

b) **Interaction = Interaction**

Furthermore, if you had to think about the frequency of interaction between stakeholders, choose a level from 1 to 3, where 1 =No interaction/ Very rare, 2 = Average (moderate) interaction, 3 =Frequent interaction

c) **Attitude = Attitude**

Within the project, you have interacted numerous times with stakeholders. What was their attitude towards the project you conducted?, where 1 =Negative, 2 = Neutral, 3 =Positive

d) **Knowledge regarding the project**

You interacted with stakeholders in carrying out project activities. If you were to evaluate their level of knowledge regarding the topics covered (knowledge of the context, risks, solutions), what would it be?

1 =No/ Minimum level of knowledge, 2 = Average level of knowledge, 3 =High level of knowledge level

e) **Interest in the project**

To what extent do you think stakeholders were interested in your project?

1 =No/minimum interest, 2 =Average interest, 3 =High interest

f) **Position**

Refers to the stakeholder’s position as a supporter or opponent of the project.

1 = Opponent, 2 = Neutral, 3 = Supporter

4) Reconnecting with the experience you had with the stakeholders you interacted with to achieve the objectives of your project, please consider

Conflict ●

Complementarity ●

Cooperation ●

No connection/Neutral ●

Stakeholder group 1

....

Stakeholder group n

Stakeholder group 1

...

Stakeholder group n

Stakeholder category	Interest					Power							
	<i>Land function</i>					<i>Types of power</i>			<i>Sources of power</i>				
	Production	Dwelling	Biodiversity conservation	Cultural	Carrier (transportation, industrial sites)	Coercive power	Compensatory power	Conditioning power	Charisma (authority of their personality)	Property (goods, money)	Expertise	Management position and/ or membership*	Family, peers
Stakeholder category 1													
....													
Stakeholder category n													

* Management position in a company/institution and/ or membership in an NGO, church, or association
 1 =Low/ insignificant 2 = Moderate 3 =High

one of the following terms that could define the relationships between them.

[Actor-linkage matrix below]

5) It is said that there are various means through which we can obtain what we want. Thus, we can discuss the so-called types of power:

Coercive power = gaining influence through threats and emotional, financial, and physical punishments.

Compensatory/ Reward power = operating through symbolic, financial, and material rewards, such as salaries, bribes, or various gifts. = submission through the granting of a reward or payment.

Conditioning power = operating through manipulating beliefs and perceptions, for example, through close groups, cultural norms, education, advertising, or propaganda.

These types of power are accessed through various means or sources, including personality (charisma, intelligence, etc.), leadership positions (pressure), money, or affiliation with an organization.

Now, consider stakeholders' different levels of interest in land functions in your project. Please answer the following question: What types of power and sources of power did the stakeholder use in your project?

6. Now, think about the project you participated in and respond to the following questions.

6.1 How would you characterize the atmosphere in the project network?

6.2 Did you consider stakeholder analysis as part of project management in this project?

6.3 If so, what has been the most challenging aspect of stakeholder analysis?

6.4 If not, looking back at the progress of the project, do you think such an analysis would have been necessary?

6.5 What issues would have required more attention about stakeholder analysis (stakeholder identification, participation, identification of their needs, and relationships between them)?

6.6 If I were the magical goldfish and I could make your project successful or remove certain obstacles, what are two things you would ask me?

Thank you for your time!

Table 1

A. Actor linkage matrix for APU project

	Farmers	NGOs	Local business people	Local public administration	Academia	Land investors	CPA_Enviro	NARW
Farmers								
NGOs								
Local business people								
Local public administration								
Academia								
Land investors								
CPA_Enviro								
NARW								

*There was no possibility to track the relationship

Conflict Complementarity Cooperation No connection

Annex 2. . Actor linkage matrix for each project

Table 2

A. Actor linkage matrix for the BITransylv project

	Farmers	NGOs	Local business people	Local public administration	Academia	CPA_Agri	CPA_Enviro	Forest Directorate	NRIAC	Pre-university educational institutions	Local community
Farmers	Complementarity	Conflict	No connection	Complementarity	No connection	Cooperation	Conflict	No connection	No connection	No connection	Complementarity
NGOs		Cooperation	No connection	Cooperation	Cooperation	No connection	Complementarity	Conflict	No connection	Cooperation	Cooperation
Local business people			Complementarity	Complementarity	No connection	Complementarity	Complementarity	Complementarity	No connection	No connection	Complementarity
Local public administration				Complementarity	Cooperation	Complementarity	Complementarity	Complementarity	Complementarity	Cooperation	Cooperation
Academia					Cooperation	No connection	No connection	Cooperation	No connection	Cooperation	No connection
CPA_Agri						No connection	Complementarity	Complementarity	Complementarity	No connection	Complementarity
CPA_Enviro							No connection	Complementarity	Complementarity	No connection	Conflict
Forest Directorate								No connection	Complementarity	No connection	No connection
NRIAC									No connection	No connection	No connection
Pre-university educational institutions										Complementarity	Cooperation
Local community											Cooperation

Conflict ● Complementarity ● Cooperation ● No connection ●

Table 3

A. Actor linkage matrix for ApeBi project

	Farmers	NGOs	Local business people	Local public administration	Academia	Land investors	CPA_Enviro	Forest Directorate	NARW
Farmers	Complementarity	Cooperation	Cooperation	Cooperation	No connection	No connection	Conflict	No connection	No connection
NGOs		Cooperation	No connection	Conflict	No connection	No connection	Conflict	Conflict	Conflict
Local business people			Cooperation	Cooperation	No connection	Cooperation	Conflict	No connection	Cooperation
Local public administration				Complementarity	No connection	Cooperation	Conflict	No connection	Cooperation
Academia					No connection	No connection	Cooperation	Conflict	Conflict
Land investors						Cooperation	Conflict	No connection	Cooperation
CPA_Enviro							Complementarity	Cooperation	Cooperation
Forest Directorate								Complementarity	No connection
NARW									Complementarity

Conflict ● Complementarity ● Cooperation ● No connection ●

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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